

Good Scientific Presentation

Version: V1

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Goal

For scientists and clinicians, to prepare a presentation and to give a talk is very important - for example, to exchange ideas with colleagues, in a group or to present their own results at a conference. The aim of a scientific presentation is to enter into a discourse and professional exchange with the audience. This is especially successful if the presentation is of a high quality. How do you create a high-quality presentation?

The publication "**Good Scientific Presentation**" was created with the aim of supporting the preparation and holding of scientific lectures and to increase the quality of presentations in the medical-scientific environment, in the spirit of Evidence-based medicine (EBM).

The detailed article - which includes a more comprehensive theoretical and practical section as well as a checklist - is published in Zenodo and can be downloaded for free [1].

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Create a presentation

A presentation will be good if you think about who your audience is and what the core message is before creating it (Take Home Message). This makes it easier to focus on the essentials and serves as a throughline when giving the presentation.

It makes a difference whether you are speaking to researchers, practitioners, students, actors, patients or a mixed audience. Depending on the target audience, different knowledge and interests can be assumed, which must be taken into account in the presentation.

With a good scientific presentation, you take the audience with you and enter into a productive - scientific and professional - exchange with them.

The basis for a successful scientific presentation is an easy-to-read, well-structured and pleasantly designed presentation. However, there are **formal, structural, and content-related requirements** for each presentation:

Formal requirements are the type of event (lecture, workshop, discussion event, etc.), duration of the lecture, presentation program, presentation format, technical possibilities or implementation, submission deadlines and procedures in advance, if applicable, etc.

The **structure of a presentation** of empirical data is essentially identical to the structure of scientific publications. Make sure to present the results neutrally and without judgement in the results section. The interpretation of your results should be presented separately in the discussion section.

A presentation is created with a suitable presentation program and consists of these sections:

- Title slide
- Introduction
- Aim and Question
- Methods
- Presentation of results
- Discussion
- Conclusion
- Conflict of interest and research funding

The 'Methods' section is the basis for evaluating and classifying your results. Therefore, the accurate description of the methods is essential and important. Only by presenting the methods used in detail can the results and conclusions be understood. In particular, you must precisely describe the **content of your study**, the 'design of the study' (study design). This is achieved in six areas [2]:

1. Question
2. Study type
3. Case number estimation or case number planning
4. Observation Unit
5. Sample/Study Population
6. Measurement

Content-related aspects, the design and the associated quality of a study can be assessed with the PICO concept as an alternative to categorisation into six areas ('design of the study') [3,4].

Create slides with a presentation program

A well-designed, high-quality presentation is the centerpiece of your presentation.

- **Create a clear, meaningful and high-quality presentation with a suitable presentation program.**
- A **good presentation** is structured, easy to read - even in the last row! - and as 'calm' as possible. You can achieve this by changing the font, font size and colour sparingly. Do not use bright or pale colour and ensure a uniform indentation. A successful presentation contains well-crafted and clearly designed slides.
- At the **end of a presentation**, there should be a slide with one (or more) "Take Home Message(s)". This allows the audience to keep the most important aspects in mind and take them into account in practice if necessary.
- **Familiarize yourself with the presentation program and its possibilities!**
- **Figures and graphics** are tied to your data and results and you should present them objectively, clearly and as simply as possible → **content beats beauty!**
- **Design of the presentation:** Suitable icons, emojis, images, photos and graphics will liven up your presentation and make it clearer. A good basis for loosening up the slides is provided, for example, by the platforms
 Pixabay: <https://pixabay.com/de/>,
 Pexels: <https://www.pexels.com/de-de/>,
 FLATICON: <https://www.flaticon.com/>.

The article 'Use images free of charge and royalty-free' provides valuable information on media that can be used free of charge, including the important topic of copyright [5].

- **Copyright:** You must pay attention to the correct citation and protection of copyright when using third-party images and graphics, see also <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/ccllicenses>.

Give a presentation

You will gain confidence and a feeling for the course and duration of your presentation if you - yourself or your colleagues - give the presentation as a rehearsal before the actual presentation. You can check whether your presentation fulfils important content and formal criteria with the help of a checklist specially developed for this purpose [1].

Before giving the lecture, familiarize yourself well with the room (size, lighting conditions, presentation desk, etc.) and the available technology.

The use of suitable shortcuts makes it easier for you to use and operate the program - even during the lecture! (see Figure 1)

Stick to the allotted time! Stop the time it takes to rehearse the lecture. This will help you develop a feeling for the length of your presentation.

If you are familiar with the technology and possibilities of the software, can operate it confidently and know important commands from the menu as well as suitable shortcuts, this expands your possibilities.

Speak calmly, clearly and distinctly. By emphasizing important points, you can control the attention of the listeners in a targeted manner. Don't talk too fast and give your audience time to process the information. Show that you are well versed in the subject matter, remain friendly and approachable to your audience.

Conclusion

Presenting and discussing your own or other people's results from research work is very important and can succeed with the tips and tricks presented. This will help you stay calm and composed during your presentation.

We wish you every success and good luck with your presentation!

Literature

[1] Röhrig, B., Exner, A.-K., Klemmt, M. (2025). Good scientific presentation: Criteria, Checklist, Tips and Tricks. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064617>, DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15064617

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[4] JBI GLOBAL WIKI. 5.2.3.1 Identifying your eligibility criteria / PICO framework. Joanna Briggs Institute. <https://jbi-global-wiki.refined.site/space/MANUAL/355861805/5.2.3.1+Identifying+your+eligibility+criteria+%252F+PICO+framework>; Call: 03.06.2025

[5] Röhrig, B. (2025). Use images for free and royalty-free. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851966>, DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14851966

Figure 1: Useful shortcuts for presenting with 'Power Point'

Start the presentation

- Start the presentation: <F5>
- Start the presentation, from current slide: <Shift+F5>

During the presentation

- Calling up the menu with further commands right mouse button
- Next Slide/forwards: <Spacebar>, <ENTER button ↵>, <Page button ↓>, <Page button →>, left mouse button
- Last slide/backwards: <Page button ↑>, <Page button ←>
- Start of the presentation (first slide): <Pos1>
- End of the presentation (last slide): <End>
- Switching to a specific page: Page number+ <ENTER button ↵>
- Complete overview of the slides: <g>
- Hide
 - with black background:
 - with white background: <f>
 - return to presentation: any key
- End the presentation: <ESC>

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